

Acute Management of Labium Superioris Oris Inflammation Through Ayurveda A Case Report

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Abstract:

Background: Acute lip swelling in children is rare but clinically significant, with causes ranging from infection and angioedema to idiopathic inflammation. Ayurveda describes such swellings under *Śoṭha*, particularly *Lūṭa-viṣa-janya śoṭha* (sudden toxic-inflammatory edema). **Case Presentation:** A 4-year-5-month-old female presented with acute painful swelling, redness, and tenderness of the upper lip since morning. There was no history of trauma, insect bite, food allergy, systemic illness, or odontogenic pathology. General and systemic examinations were unremarkable. Based on classical Ayurvedic principles, the condition was correlated with *Lūṭa-viṣa-janya śoṭha*. **Intervention:** Management included topical application of a paste prepared from Bilwadi Gulika (a traditional polyherbal formulation with *Viśahara* and *Śoṭahara* actions) and freshly crushed Tulsi (*Ocimum sanctum*) leaves, applied four times over 24 hours. **Outcome:** Marked symptomatic relief was observed within hours. Pain and swelling reduced after the second application, with near-complete resolution by 12 hours and complete recovery within 24 hours. No adverse drug reactions were reported. **Conclusion:** This case demonstrates the effectiveness of an Ayurvedic protocol using Bilwadi Gulika and Tulsi paste in managing acute lip inflammation in a pediatric patient. The rapid, safe, and non-invasive outcome suggests potential for Ayurvedic interventions in acute pediatric inflammatory conditions.

Keywords : Labium superioris inflammation, *Ayurveda*, *Bilwadi Gulika*.

Introduction: Acute swelling of lip in pediatric patients is relatively rare but clinically important due to its wide range of potential etiologies. The lips are sensitive structure and highly vascular, sudden enlargement can result from infection, inflammation, allergic reaction or idiopathic mechanisms. Infection (cellulitis and odontogenic infection) often present with progressive pain, edema, tenderness, may be associated with fever¹. On the other hand, angioedema represents an immunologically mediated cause, usually characterized by rapid, nonpitting swelling sometimes painless and associated with airways involvement². In certain cases, sudden inflammatory edema of lip may occur without any clear etiology, resolving rapidly with local or systemic therapy. From ayurveda perspective, such types of swelling are described under *soṭha* (localized inflammatory edema), which may arise due to dosha vitiation, *viṣa* specially, *viśaja soṭha* and *lūṭa viṣa janya soṭha* are mentioned in classics as sudden-onset painful, reddish swelling that develop without evident trauma. therapeutic measures in such cases traditionally include the

administration of detoxifying and anti-inflammatory formulations. *Bilwadi Gulika*, a polyherbal preparation indicates in toxicological and inflammatory disorders³ and *tulsi* (*ocimum sanctum*), widely recognized for its antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory and anti-oxidant properties.⁴ Documentation of this case is important, as they highlight both the clinical dilemmas in differentiating acute lip swelling in children and therapeutic potential of ayurvedic approaches.

Case study:

A 4year 5months old female patient approached to hospital with her parent with chief complains of severe pain and swelling over the upper lip, redness, tenderness at that region noticed since morning by patient mother. There is no history of trauma, insect bite, new food intake or systemic illness as per her mother, no significant family history was noticed & socioeconomic status is middle-class family with good hygiene.

Prenatal, natal and post-natal history:

There is no significant history related to complains, mother conceived at the age of 32 had regular checkups & took supplements (iron, folic acid) which suggested by doctor, there was no history of eclampsia, gestational Diabetes, hypertension. The delivery of child was normal.

Current status:

All milestones developed normally, socially active and child is on food but, sometimes drink mother milk.

Clinical findings:

The general examination indicated, child was well nourished, systemic examination showed that the patient was conscious and oriented to person, place, time. Vital examination showed blood pressure of 102/74mmHg, pulse rate 82/min, with respiratory rate 19/min and normal body temperature, no any significant finding noticed on respiratory and cardiovascular examination.

On location examination – Diffuse swelling of labium superioris oris, redness, local warmth and tenderness present, no fever, rash, oral cavity normal no findings were noticed in oral cavity.

Asthasthana pareeksha:

Nadi: vatapittaja

Mala: grathita

Mutra: prakrita

Jiwaha: alipta

Shabdha: spastha

Sparsh: samsheetaushna

Dhrik: prakrita

Akruti: prakrita

Dashavidha pareeksha:

Prakruti: pittavataj

Vikruti: pittapradhana vata

Sara: Madhyama

Samhanana: Madhyama

Satva; Madhyama

Satmya: Madhyama

Ahara shakti: pravara

Vyayama shakti: Madhyama

Vaya: balya

No other clinical finding was noted.

Diagnostic Assessment:

On the basis of complaints and clinical findings of patient, angioedema (painless and sometime itching is present but, in patient pain was present), traumatic (but no history of trauma), odontogenic (no any tooth problem) after over viewing the above symptoms the present case was Acute labium superius oris inflammation is also called Cheilitis and compared *with Luta Visha Janya Shotha* as per ayurveda and treatment was planned accordingly.

Therapeutic intervention

The treatment followed the classical Ayurvedic management of *Luta Visha* as the initial diagnosis was based on suspected localized inflammation without an apparent cause.

Medications Administered:

Bilwadi Gulika: Known for its effectiveness in neutralizing toxic effects (*Visha Hara*) and reducing inflammation. *Tulsi* Leaves (*Ocimum sanctum*): *Tulsi* is widely recognized for its anti-inflammatory (*Shothahara*), antitoxic (*Visha Hara*), and antipyretic (*Jwaraghni*) properties.

Method of Administration: A paste made from *Bilwadi Gulika* and freshly crushed *Tulsi* leaves (4-5 leaves) was applied externally on the affected area. Application frequency: Four times within 24 hours.

Table 1: Treatment Protocol and Observations

Time	Intervention Method	Response
6:45 AM	Baseline	Severe swelling, pain, irritability Unable to eat
7:00 AM	1 st application	Reapplied Swelling reduced, pain mild, liquids taken
10:30 AM	2 nd application	Reapplied Swelling reduced, pain mild, liquids taken
3:00 PM	3 rd application	Reapplied Redness minimal, child playful
10:00 PM	4 th application	Reapplied Near complete resolution, normal eating

VAS score:

1. Pre- application: 8/10
2. After 1st application: 7.5/10
3. After 2nd application: 6/10
4. After 3rd application: 3/10
5. After 4th application: 1/10
6. Next day without application: no pain

Treatment compliance and adverse events: child tolerated the therapy well and no ADR (adverse drug reaction) was noticed.

3. Results

Table 2: Symptom Grading Before and After Treatment

Symptom	Morning 6:45 AM	After 10:30 AM	After 10:00 PM
Swelling (<i>Shotha</i>)	Severe (+++)	Moderate (++)	Minimal (+)
Pain (<i>Shoola</i>)	Severe (+++)	Mild (+)	Nil (0)
Redness (<i>Raga</i>)	marked (+++)	Mild (+)	Absent (0)
Feeding	Unable	Liquid only	Normal solids
Irritability	Present	Reduced	Absent

Outcome: >80% improvement within 12 hrs; complete by 24 hrs.

Discussion:

This case demonstrates the efficacy of Ayurvedic medication in the acute management of labial inflammation. The combination of *Bilwadi Gulika* and *Tulsi* leaves worked synergistically to reduce swelling and pain. *Bilwadi Gulika* has traditionally been used for treating toxic bites (*Lutha Keeta Visha Nashni*) and in this case, it provided anti-inflammatory, detoxifying, and pain-relieving effects.

Table 03: *Bilwadi Gulika* contents:

Drugs	Anti-inflammatory action
Curcuma longa (<i>haridra</i>)	Curcumin inhibits the NF-kB and Cox-2 pathways, leading to reduced pro-inflammatory cytokines such as TNF-alpha and IL-6 ⁵ .
Zingiber officinale (<i>sunthi</i>)	Gingerols and shogaols inhibit prostaglandin synthesis, thereby reduced edema and pain ⁶ .
Piper longum (<i>pippali</i>)	Piperine enhanced the bioavailability of curcumin and modulates inflammatory mediators by inhibiting the NF-kB and MAPK signaling pathway ⁷ .
Aegle marmelos (<i>vilwa</i>)	Alkaloids in aegle marmelos reduced oxidative stress and inflammatory markers, exhibiting anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties ⁸ .
<i>Triphala</i>	Triphala exhibits antioxidant and anti-inflammatory effect by scavenging free radicals and modulating immune responses ⁹ .

Ocimum sanctum (tulsi):

Tulsi has proven *Vishaghni* (antitoxic) properties that further enhance the paste's ability to treat inflammation and reduce fever or discomfort. Together, they offered a rapid and effective response without the need for conventional pharmaceuticals

It exhibits significant anti-inflammatory properties through multiple molecular pathways. Key bioactive compounds such as eugenol, ursolic acid, and linalool have been identified in tulsi leaves and essential oils also. These compounds modulate inflammatory responses by inhibiting the NF-kB signaling pathway, which play an important role in transcription of pro-inflammatory like TNF-alpha and IL-6. Additionally, *tulsi* compounds suppress the activity of cyclooxygenase-2 (COX-2) and lipoxygenase (LOX) enzymes, leading to reduced synthesis of pro-inflammatory mediators such as prostaglandins and leukotrienes¹⁰.

Conclusion:

The successful resolution of acute upper lip inflammation, in a pediatric patient through the external application of *Bilwadi Gulika* and *Tulsi* paste illustrates the potential of Ayurvedic for managing localized inflammatory conditions. The results seen within a single day highlight the approach's effectiveness, especially in pediatric care.

Declaration of patient consent: Guardian consent was obtained for publication of clinical details. Identity is anonymized.

Patient Perspective: The child's mother observed visible relief within hours and expressed satisfaction with the safe, herbal approach without injections or antibiotics.

Conflict Of Interest: None.

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